

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES OF OXIDES OF CHROMIUM

BY S. K. K. JĀTKAR AND V. B. MAINKAR

Chrome alum has been titrated with potassium chromate and chromic acid and *vice versa* using the cell: Pt-sol- K_2SO_4 (saturated)- NH_2SO_4 -Hg $_2$ SO $_4$ -Hg. The nature of the E. M. F. and the $\Delta E/\Delta$ c.c. curve has been found to be very complex. The peaks observed, which are reproducible, would indicate the formation of a large number of compounds of the general formula $aCrO_3 \cdot bCr_2O_3$.

These curves would further indicate that the chromium ion in solution undergoes striking changes of electronic structure, with progressive oxidation.

The existence of a number of compounds between chromic oxide Cr_2O_3 and chromic anhydride CrO_3 has been indicated by a number of investigations.

The results are summarised in the following table (cf. *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1939, 22A, 291).

TABLE I

Formula.	Structural formula.	Formula.	Structural formula.
CrO_3	CrO_3	Cr_4O_6	$2CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$
	$36CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$	Cr_5O_8	$CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$
	$20CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$	Cr_9O_{16}	$2Cr_2O_3 \cdot 3Cr_2O_3$
	$16CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$	Cr_7O_{12}	$CrO_3 \cdot 2Cr_2O_3$
Cr_3O_{21}	$6CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$		$CrO_3 \cdot 3Cr_2O_3$
	$5CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$		$CrO_3 \cdot 4Cr_2O_3$
Cr_4O_{18}	$4CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$	Cr_3O_8	Cr_2O_3
Cr_5O_{12}	$3CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$		

The general formula of chromium chromates corresponding to the various steps observed in the decomposition of CrO_3 can be expressed by the formulae $aCrO_3 \cdot bCr_2O_3$ where the values of "a" in former case are 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6.....n and "b" from 1 to 4. Maus (*Pog. Ann.*, 1827, 9, 127) prepared Cr_8O_{15} ($4CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3$) by evaporating a solution of hydrated chromic oxide or chromium carbonate in cold aqueous solution of chromic acid, and $CrO_3 \cdot (CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3)$ by digesting a hot solution of potassium chromate with chromic acid. Bensch (*ibid.*, 1842, 55, 98) digested chromium sulphate with chromic acid to obtain CrO_3 , while Eliot and Storer (*Proc. Amer. Acad.*, 1862, 5, 207) replaced the chromium sulphate by chrome alum.

The brown powder obtained by Rammelsberg (*Pog. Ann.*, 1846, 68, 274) by mixing chrome alum and potassium dichromate was considered to be $2Cr_2O_3 \cdot$

$3\text{CrO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, but Eliot and Storer (*loc. cit.*) showed it to be probably a mixture. Popp (*Annalen*, 1848, 66, 87) observed that on exposing chromic anhydride on a glass plate, it dried to a brown crust, insoluble in water and having a composition Cr_5O_{15} ($2\text{CrO}_3 \cdot 3\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$). It is also obtained by treating a solution of chromic acid with an excess of alcohol at room temperature and heating the mixture after the evolution of aldehyde is complete. After suitable treatment the greenish brown oxide is obtained.

Seubert and Carstens (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 50, 66) presumed that CrO_3 was formed at an intermediate stage during the reduction of chromic anhydride by iodide or hydrazine; but Leuther and Rutter (*ibid.*, 1907, 52, 440; 54, 29) preferred the assumption that the reduction proceeded through stages of sexi, quinque, quadri and trivalent chromium.

Calcagni (*Gazzetta*, 1925, 55, 226) prepared $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ i. e. ($6\text{CrO}_3 \cdot \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$) by evaporating a solution of chromic oxide in chromic acid. Blanc (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1926, vi, 10, 82) recorded that when a salt of trivalent chromium was added to a solution of a neutral chromate and the precipitate washed with boiling water, brown $2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{CrO}_3$ was formed.

The chemical properties of the various chromium chromates formed have not so far been systematically investigated though the solubility of the oxides in various reagents has been worked out. Traube (*Annalen*, 1845, 66, 89) observed that $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{CrO}_3$ was insoluble in water and converted into a soluble modification by keeping in contact with water for a long time. Braun (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1853, i, 90, 856) observed that $4\text{CrO}_3 \cdot \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolved slightly in cold water, and showed a greater solubility in boiling water. Döbereiner (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 62, 440) observed that Cr_5O_{12} ($3\text{CrO}_3 \cdot \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$) dissolved in hot water with the formation of a solution of colloidal nature. Simon and Schmidt (*ibid.*, 1924, 152, 191) observed that Cr_5O_{12} was partly soluble in hot water. The results show that there is a slow action of water on the oxides, forming a corresponding acid, which is soluble in water to a certain extent.

Roy Chaudhari (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 652) measured the equivalent conductivity, freezing point, p_{H} value and absorption spectra of aqueous solution of $3\text{CrO}_3 \cdot \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ and concluded that the oxide was not a simple chromium chromate $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ but it was $\text{Cr}[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \cdot (\text{CrO}_4)_3]$. The oxide reacts with water to form an acid, which is soluble in water and dissociates to a slight extent; 12% of the acid formed is dissociated. The compound exists in solution at a p_{H} of 2.87, while the p_{H} of the H_2CrO_4 of same molarity is 1.82.

Hartford (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1942, 34, 920) has made p_{H} measurements on $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ i. e. $6\text{CrO}_3 \cdot \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$. He points out that the solution of chromic dichromate shows decreasing p_{H} with time. The chromium chromate was prepared by various methods such as thermal decomposition, electrolytic reduction and reduction with H_2O_2 , methyl alcohol and oxalic acid. In all cases

exceptionally high hydrogen-ion activity was noticed. It is stated that insoluble basic chromates precipitate from the dichromate solutions at p_H values above 3. Earlier studies of the compound postulate an undissociated solute or colloid, but the high hydrogen-ion activity points to a highly ionised solute, while, the slow change in p_H on standing gives indication of a rearrangement of a complex solute. The p_H of this solution is below 2. Finally at p_H 3.35 the colloidal basic chromate $Cr_2(OH)_4 \cdot CrO_4$ forms. In view of the ease with which complex chromium chromates are formed, even in highly acid solution, it is concluded that in chromic dichromate solutions there exists a progressive hydrolysis in which the two chromate complexes form from the dichromate complex. In complete accord with this hypothesis is the low p_H at equilibrium of chromium dichromate.

From thermal and chemical formation and properties of the various chromium chromates, it seems possible to find out if the substances give due indication of their presence by a potentiometric titration of K_2CrO_4 or chromic acid by chrome alum.

The reactions occurring at the various stages may be represented by equations like the following :—

- (1) $4Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + K_2CrO_4 + 11H_2O = CrO_3 \cdot 4Cr_2O_3 + K_2SO_4 + 11H_2SO_4$
- (2) $3Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + K_2CrO_4 + 8H_2O = CrO_3 \cdot 3Cr_2O_3 + K_2SO_4 + 8H_2SO_4$
- (3) $Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + K_2CrO_4 + 2H_2O = CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3 + K_2SO_4 + 2H_2SO_4$
- (4) $Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + 2K_2CrO_4 + H_2O = 2CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3 + 2K_2SO_4 + H_2SO_4$
- (5) $Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + 3K_2CrO_4 = 3CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3 + 3K_2SO_4$
- (6) $Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + 6K_2CrO_4 + 3H_2O = 6CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3 + 3K_2SO_4 + 6KOH$
- (7) $Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + 36K_2CrO_4 + 33H_2O = 36CrO_3 \cdot Cr_2O_3 + 3K_2SO_4 + 66KOH$

EXPERIMENTAL

The potentiometric titration was carried out by using the electrode system :

The potentials were measured on a Tinsley vernier potentiometer using a sensitive mirror galvanometer as null instrument. Chrome alum was titrated with K_2CrO_4 or chromic acid or *vice versa*.

Figures 1 to 5 show the plot of E. M. F. and $\Delta E / \Delta c.c.$ against c.c. of titrant. The summary is given in Tables II and III.

Table II shows the comparison of the observed volume the of reagent added to obtain the peak with that calculated on the assumption that the compound has a composition shown in column 1.

TABLE II

$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ (calc.)	10 c.c. M/60- chrome alum + M/30-chromate or chromic acid (calc.)	10 c.c. M/60- chrome alum + M/30-Aq K_2CrO_4 (obsd.).	10 c.c. M/60- chrome alum + M/30-alk. K_2CrO_4 (obsd.).	10 c.c. M/60- chrome alum + M/30-chromic acid (corr.) observed.	75 c.c. M/30- K_2CrO_4 or chro- mic acid + M/60- chrome alum (calc.)	75 c.c. M/30-aq K_2CrO_4 + M/60- chrome alum (observed).	75 c.c. M/30-chro- mic acid + M/60- chrome alum (observed).
0.25	1.25 c.c.	1.15 c.c.	1.05 c.c.	1.05 c.c.
0.33	1.66	1.65	1.65	1.75
0.50	2.50	2.60	2.40	2.30
0.66	3.33	3.45	3.30	2.95
1	5.00	...	4.70	4.95
2	10.00	10.10	9.80	9.80	75.00 c.c.	74.90 c.c.	74.55 c.c.
3	15.00	14.90	15.30	14.80	50.00	49.50	49.45
4	20.00	20.30	20.20	21.00	37.50	37.50	37.45
5	25.00	24.70	25.10	25.30	30.00	29.90	29.65
6	30.00	29.90	29.60	31.40	25.00	24.70	24.45
7	21.40	21.10	21.15
8	18.70	18.30	18.65
9	16.70	16.70	16.55
10	15.00	14.90	14.95
11	13.60	13.50	13.75
12	12.50	12.50	12.05
13	11.50	11.50	11.55
14	10.70	10.50	...
15	75.00	74.70	10.00	...	10.05
16	9.40	9.50	...
17	8.80	8.70	...
18	8.10	8.10	...
20	7.50	7.50	...
22	6.80	6.80	...
26	5.80	5.70	5.05
32	4.70	4.70	...
36	4.15	4.10	...
43	3.50	3.50	3.45
64	2.30	2.10	1.75
125	1.20	1.10	1.05
216	0.65	...	0.65

FIG. 1

CC. of $K_2Cr_2O_7$

FIG. 2

CC. H_2CrO_4

FIG. 4

FIG. 3

TABLE III

Formula.	Decimal formula (CrO _x .)	Ratio CrO ₃ /Cr ₂ O ₃ (calc.)	Ratio CrO ₃ /Cr ₂ O ₃ (observed.)				
			Chrome alum + aq K ₂ CrO ₄ .	Chrome alum + alk. K ₂ CrO ₄ .	Chrome alum + chromic acid.	Aq. K ₂ CrO ₄ + chrome alum.	Chromic acid + chrome alum.
Cr ₂ O ₃	CrO _{1.500}
Cr ₃ O ₁₃	CrO _{1.666}	0.25	0.23 (18)	0.21(-40)	0.20(45)
Cr ₇ O ₃₂	CrO _{1.714}	0.33	0.33 (-6)	0.33(-70)	0.33(40)
Cr ₅ O ₉	CrO _{1.800}	0.50	0.55 (-13)	0.49(-40)	0.44(27)
Cr ₈ O ₁₅	CrO _{1.875}	0.66	0.69 (-15)	0.67(-25)	0.56(25.5)
Cr ₃ O ₆	CrO _{2.000}	1.	...	0.95(-40)	0.95(25)
Cr ₄ O ₉	CrO _{2.250}	2.	2.01 (-10)	1.99(-15)	1.87(10)	1.98(5)	1.97(-4)
Cr ₅ O ₁₂	CrO _{2.400}	3.	2.99 (-6)	3.10(-15)	2.83(10)	2.99(2)	2.97(-3)
Cr ₆ O ₁₅	CrO _{2.500}	4.	4.08 (-4)	4.09(-6.5)	4.02(5)	3.95(15)	3.92(-4)
Cr ₇ O ₁₉	CrO _{2.571}	5.	4.98 (-3.5)	5.09(-69.5)	4.85(5)	4.96(10.5)	4.95(-3)
Cr ₈ O ₂₁	CrO _{2.625}	6.	6.00 (7)	6.00(-15)	6.00(3.3)	6.00(11.5)	6.00(-5)
Cr ₉ O ₂₄	CrO _{2.666}	7.	7.02(7)	6.94(-2)
Cr ₁₀ O ₂₇	CrO _{2.700}	8.	8.10(6)	7.87(-4)
Cr ₁₁ O ₃₀	CrO _{2.727}	9.	8.88(8.5)	8.87(-3)
Cr ₁₂ O ₃₃	CrO _{2.750}	10.	9.95(6.5)	9.81(-2)
Cr ₁₃ O ₃₆	CrO _{2.769}	11.	10.98(5)	10.52(-3)
Cr ₁₄ O ₃₉	CrO _{2.786}	12.	11.86(5)	12.17(-2)
Cr ₁₅ O ₄₂	CrO _{2.800}	13.	12.89(5.5)	12.71(-2)
Cr ₁₆ O ₄₅	CrO _{2.812}	14.	14.11(8)	...
Cr ₁₇ O ₄₈	CrO _{2.823}	15.	14.23(2)	...	14.60(-3)
Cr ₁₈ O ₅₁	CrO _{2.833}	16.	15.61(7.5)	...
Cr ₁₉ O ₅₄	CrO _{2.842}	17.	17.04(4)	...
Cr ₂₀ O ₅₇	CrO _{2.850}	18.	18.30(6.5)	...
Cr ₂₂ O ₆₃	CrO _{2.857}	20.	19.76(5)	...
Cr ₂₄ O ₆₉	CrO _{2.875}	22.	21.85(4)	...
Cr ₂₆ O ₇₅	CrO _{2.885}	26.	26.00(9)	29.05(-2)
Cr ₂₈ O ₈₁	CrO _{2.893}	32.
Cr ₃₂ O ₉₀	CrO _{2.906}	36.	31.54(6)	...
Cr ₃₆ O ₁₀₈	CrO _{2.917}	43.	36.15(8.5)	...
Cr ₄₂ O ₁₂₆	CrO _{2.929}	64.	42.36(12)	42.53(-1)
Cr ₄₈ O ₁₄₄	CrO _{2.938}	125.	70.58(18)	83.85(-4)
Cr ₁₂₇ O ₃₇₅	CrO _{2.953}	216.	134.8 (15)	139.7 (-9)
Cr ₂₁₆ O ₆₅₁	CrO _{2.963}	225.7 (-10)
CrO ₃	CrO _{3.000}

Table III shows the comparison of the calculated ratios of CrO_3 , Cr_2O_3 with that observed; the figures in parenthesis alongside represent the value of $\frac{\Delta E}{\Delta C.C.}$.

It was observed that there was no precipitate till 24 c.c. of aqueous chromate were added, to the chrome alum. A brown precipitate was obtained thereafter. A brown precipitate appeared in the case of alkaline chromate on

adding 8.5 c.c. of chromate, while with chromic acid there was no precipitation, but the solution darkened.

From the very beginning of the titration of aqueous chromate with chrome alum, there appeared a precipitate though no precipitate was observable when the chromate was replaced by chromic acid, only a darkening occurring.

D I S C U S S I O N

Datar and Jatkar (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1939, 22A, 119, 225, 287, 309) have shown that chromium chromates are comparatively stable in the presence of basic compounds. The results of the titration, where alkaline chromate is employed, prove the correctness of this conclusion, as the peaks obtained are much stronger than in other titrations.

That the chromium chromates can exist in acidic solution is brought out by the peaks obtained at the required intervals when chromic acid is employed. As is to be expected, the peaks are not very strong.

In the titration of chromate with chrome alum, several compounds have been obtained, the most remarkable of which are the oxides formed in the initial stages whose ratios correspond to the cubes of 6, 5, 4, and so on.

In the solid state the structure of CrO_3 is a slightly deformed octahedron, each metal atom being surrounded by 6 oxygen atoms and each oxygen by two metal atoms. Cr_2O_3 has the corundum structure in which six oxygen atoms form an octahedral group around the metal atom and each oxygen is surrounded by four metal atoms (cf. Wells, "Structural Inorganic Chemistry", 1945).

It is obvious that (A) CrO_3 and (B) Cr_2O_3 having similar structures can form interpenetrating lattice. Thus, we should expect a continuous series of solid compounds of the general formula A_xB_y , which have characteristic properties such as oxidation-reduction potentials, magnetic susceptibilities and vapour pressures, which would be more pronounced for the more symmetrical ones.

It is interesting to point out that the characteristic peaks occur at intervals of unit changes in composition which would indicate the building up of the lattice structure step by step. Some of these apparent compositions are related by $2^3, 3^3, 4^3, 5^3, 6^3$ i. e. ratios 8, 27, 64, 125, 216 which are roughly in agreement with the observed peaks at ratios 8, 26, 70, 134, 225. the increasing discrepancy being due to lack of closer points. It is intended to study this amazing case of periodic precipitation with the help of a continuous titration apparatus.